

Proposed Legislative Model to Decrease Air Conditioning Overcooling

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Abstract

This publication includes a proposed legislative model to decrease air conditioning overcooling.

Air conditioning is the main electricity consumer in buildings equipped with air conditioning. Overcooling below the Comfort Heat Index is not for comfort; actually it causes overcooling discomfort and a health hazard. The lower the air conditioner temperature, the longer its operating time. The proposed legislation includes four energy conservation measures:

- Heat Index-based control instead of conventional temperature-only control;
- fine-resolution control of 0.1 degree instead of the traditional 1 degree increments;
- minimum cooling temperature limit of 22°C, replacing common limits of 16°C;
- separate air conditioning control in each room.

These energy conservation measures have 55% energy saving potential, about 1,000 TWh of global electricity per year, in addition to 20% peak demand mitigation potential.

Unlike many other GHG mitigation measures, enforcement of the above measures does not involve expenses or investment; on the contrary, it significantly reduces

energy cost (mainly due to shorter operating time) and reduces investment in oversized air conditioning units.

All calculations in this work are based on the “*Online Building Energy and Heat Index Simulation and Optimization – BESOO*” version 544 with the real meteorological datasets for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, as on the sites:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/Hi>

Glossary

Ave	average
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, Heat Index which is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling, °C
ECM	Energy Conservation Measure
HI	Heat Index – air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, °C
HIC	Heat Index during cooling hours, °C
OCAC	Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning – setting of air conditioning thermostat that results in minimum air conditioning hours, minimum energy consumption, and in Heat Index below the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C)
RH	relative humidity of air, %
T	air temperature, °C

Energy Units

Generally, this work is in metric units. Calculations and application of the Heat Index involve degrees Fahrenheit.

Energy is in kWh/year, and power in kW.

Proposed Regulations

Reduction of Air Conditioning Overcooling

1. Title

These Regulations shall be cited as:

“Regulations on the Reduction of Air Conditioning Overcooling.”

2. Entry into Force

These Regulations shall enter into force two (2) years after the date of their publication.

3. Definitions

For the purposes of these Regulations:

“Air Conditioning System” or **“AC”** means any new air conditioning unit or system designed to cool indoor spaces, including, but not limited to, central air conditioning systems, split air conditioning units, and window air conditioning units.

“Heat Index (HI)” means the apparent temperature representing the combined effect of air temperature and relative humidity on human thermal comfort, calculated in accordance with Annex I.

“Comfort Heat Index” means a Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling, with a value of 26.6°C (79.9°F).

4. Heat Index Control Requirements

- 4.1 Every AC shall be equipped with:
 - a room air temperature sensor (T),
 - a room air relative humidity sensor (RH),
 - an electronic control device capable of calculating the Heat Index (HI) based on measured T and RH.
- 4.2 The calculation of the Heat Index shall be performed in accordance with the procedure set out in Annex I.
- 4.3 Every AC shall be equipped with a remote control or equivalent user interface allowing the user to set the desired Heat Index.
- 4.4 The selectable Heat Index range shall be:
 - SI units (metric): from 22.8°C to 30.0°C, with a resolution of 0.1°C; or
 - IP units (imperial): from 73.0°F to 86.0°F, with a resolution of 0.1°F.
- 4.5 The default setting upon initial activation shall be the **Comfort Heat Index**.

- 4.6 If the Heat Index setting is adjusted below the Comfort Heat Index, the system shall automatically reset to the Comfort Heat Index upon each power-off or restart.
- 4.7 The remote control shall include a dedicated button labeled “**Comfort**”, which:
- shall be the largest button on the remote control,
 - shall be colored green, and
 - shall activate or reset the system to operate at the Comfort Heat Index.
- 4.8 The Heat Index adjustment scale displayed on the remote control shall:
- indicate increments relative to the Comfort Heat Index,
 - use increments of 0.1°C or 0.1°F of Heat Index (not air temperature),
 - display values below the Comfort Heat Index in red, and
 - display values above the Comfort Heat Index in green, with the Comfort Heat Index serving as the neutral reference point.

5. Temperature and Heat Index Limits

- 5.1 The minimum allowable cooling operation conditions shall be:
- an air temperature of **22.0°C (71.6°F)**, or
 - a Heat Index of **22.8°C (73.0°F)**,
whichever is higher.

6. Separate Control by Room or Area

- 6.1 Each room in every residential, commercial, or public building shall be provided with a separate control enabling:
- independent switching off of the AC, and
 - independent adjustment of the Heat Index above or below the Comfort Heat Index.
- 6.2 In open-plan or large air-conditioned spaces, a separate Heat Index control and on/off function shall be provided for each area of up to **50 square meters**.
- 6.3 The requirements of this Section shall apply only to buildings, or parts of buildings, for which a building permit application is submitted two (2) years after the publication of these Regulations.

Annex I

Heat Index Calculation Procedure

The Heat Index shall be calculated in accordance with the most recent version of the procedure published by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Weather Service, as referenced on the NOAA website.

As of 7 December 2025, the procedure consists of the following steps:

Step 1 – Initial Calculation (Simple Formula)

Formula 1 - Steadman Formula (HI < 80°F)

$$HI = 0.5 * (TF + 61.0 + 1.2*(TF - 68.0) + 0.094*RH)$$

where:

- HI = Heat Index (°F)
- TF = air temperature (°F)
- RH = relative humidity (%) (for humidity 60%, use number 60 and not 0.60)

If the resulting HI is less than 80°F, this value shall be the final Heat Index.

If the resulting HI is equal to or greater than 80°F, proceed to Step 2.

Step 2 – Rothfusz Regression Formula

Formula 2 - Rothfusz Formula (HI ≥ 80°F)

$$HI = -42.379 + 2.04901523 * TF + 10.14333127 * RH - 0.22475541 * TF * RH - 0.00683783 * TF * TF - 0.05481717 * RH * RH + 0.00122874 * TF * TF * RH + 0.00085282 * TF * RH * RH - 0.00000199 * TF * TF * RH * RH$$

Step 3 – Low Humidity Adjustment

If RH < 13% and 80°F < TF < 112°F, apply the following correction:

Formula 3 - Low Humidity Correction

$$HI = HI_2 - ((13 - RH) / 4) * SQRT((17 - ABS(TF - 95)) / 17)$$

where HI₂ is the Heat Index calculated using Formula 2 (°F)

Step 4 – High Humidity Adjustment

If RH > 85% and 80°F < TF < 87°F, apply the following correction:

Formula 4 - High Humidity Correction

$$HI = HI_2 + ((RH - 85) / 10) * ((87 - TF) / 5)$$

Annex II

Explanatory Remarks

Air conditioning represents a major and rapidly growing component of global electricity consumption. In 2022, space cooling accounted for approximately **7.2% of global electricity consumption**, while greenhouse gas emissions associated with air conditioning, including refrigerants, represented approximately 3.2% of global emissions.

A significant share of this energy is wasted through **overcooling**, defined as cooling below thermal comfort requirements. Overcooling does not improve comfort and often results in thermal discomfort, drafts, noise, health risks from prolonged exposure, unnecessary electricity consumption, and higher energy costs. Lower cooling setpoints also significantly increase system operating hours.

The proposed Regulations introduce four Energy Conservation Measures (ECMs):

- Heat Index–based control instead of conventional temperature-only control;
- fine-resolution control (0.1°C or °F) instead of traditional 1-degree increments;
- a minimum cooling temperature limit of 22°C, replacing common limits of 16°C;
- independent control of air conditioning by room or defined area.

Together, these measures have an estimated **energy-saving potential of approximately 55%**, equivalent to roughly 1,000 TWh of electricity per year globally, as well as an estimated 20% reduction in peak electricity demand.

Unlike many greenhouse gas mitigation measures, these ECMs require no additional operational expenditure and may reduce capital costs by avoiding oversized air conditioning systems, while delivering immediate economic and environmental benefits.

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End of text of the proposed regulations

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Online Building Energy and Heat Index Simulation and Optimization – BESOO

All data in this work are simulation results for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv applying the program “*Online Building Energy and Heat Index Simulation and Optimization – BESOO*” version 544 [7].

Table 1 - Example of results table of BESOO simulation for Jerusalem [7]

15/12/2025 05:28:07 NY			
nowagreen.ct.ws BESOO page 544Jm, v F544Jm01 Comfort Heat Index (CHI), unlimited cooling			
period thermostatic control			
CoolT	25.5	°C	Cool On
URL	https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	109.61	hours	TTC
start day	20230207		
last day	20240206		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
Cooling			
cooling start date	20230517		
cooling end date	20231029		
cooling hours in the simulation period	978		11%
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	388	kWh thermal	50%
quantity of condense during cooling	572	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	394	kWh thermal	50%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	782	kWh thermal	100%
Max 10min Cool power [W thermal]	807	20230908	19:40
Max 10min power for condense [W thermal]	1382	20230813	20:10
Max 10min power for cooling and for condense	1945	20230729	18:40
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.13	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	984	hours	11%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	26.56	20230813	20:10
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	24.37	20230728	11:20
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours		°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	0	hours	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.13	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	984	hours	11%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling hours			
Ave HIO above CHI		°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	0	hours	0%
Max HIO above CHI °C	0	0	0
Ventilation			
ventilation hours	2968	hours	34%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without cooling	7782	hours	89%
comfort hours without cooling or ventilation	4814	hours	55%

Table 2 - Example of results table of BESOO simulation for Tel Aviv [7]

14/12/2025 16:18:46 NY			
nowagreen.ct.ws BESOO page 544TA, v F544TA01 Comfort Heat Index (CHI), unlimited cooling period thermostatic control			
CoolT	25.5	°C	Cool On
URL	https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	22.64	hours	TTC
start day	20230214		
last day	20240213		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
Cooling			
cooling start date	20230228		
cooling end date	20231118		
cooling hours in the simulation period	2695		31%
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	1418	kWh thermal	35%
quantity of condense during cooling	3859	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	2656	kWh thermal	65%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	4074	kWh thermal	100%
Max 10min Cool power [W thermal]	1032	20230908	17:40
Max 10min power for condense [W thermal]	2071	20230717	18:20
Max 10min power for cooling and for condense	2986	20230908	20:10
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.9	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	2709	hours	31%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	26.48	20231014	21:00
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	24.42	20230527	10:00
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours		°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	0	hours	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.9	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	2709	hours	31%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling hours			
Ave HIO above CHI		°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	0	hours	0%
Max HIO above CHI °C	0	0	0
Ventilation			
ventilation hours	2505	hours	29%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without cooling	6065	hours	69%
comfort hours without cooling or ventilation	3560	hours	41%

Energy Consumption of Air Conditioning

All data in this section are from the publication “Air conditioning causes around 3% of greenhouse gas emissions. How will this change in the future?” [8].

Table 3 - AC energy consumption and GHG emissions [8]

number of AC units in the world in 2024	2,000,000,000	units
projected number of AC units in the world in 2050	5,500,000,000	units
global electricity consumption 2022	29,000	TWh/y
AC consumption in 2022	2,100	TWh/y
AC consumption in 2022	7.2%	
AC consumption per unit	1,050	kWh/y
projected AC electricity consumption in 2050	5,775	TWh/y
AC electricity to world electricity (2022)	7.2%	
AC CO2 emissions in 2022	1,020,000,000	T CO2/y
AC CO2 emissions to world (2022)	2.70%	
AC refrigerants GHG emissions	720,000,000	tCO2eq/y
AC total GHG emissions (2022)	1,740,000,000	tCO2eq/y
AC GHG emissions including refrigerants to world (2022)	3.20%	

Heat Index

Heat Index (HI) is the apparent temperature representing the combined effect of air temperature and relative humidity on human thermal comfort, expressed in “feel like” degrees Celsius or Fahrenheit.

The procedure for the determination of the Heat Index is in Annex I of the proposed regulations “*Heat Index Calculations Procedure*” [1].

More about the Heat Index may be found in the publications [2] and [4].

Comfort Heat Index

“*Comfort Heat Index*” (CHI) means the Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling. CHI is a Heat Index value of 26.6°C (79.9°F).

The issue of Comfort Heat Index is described in detail in the publication “*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [4].

Following is the recommendation of the publication [4] for the Comfort Heat Index (CHI):

Table 4 - Comfort Heat Index [4]

Comfort Heat Index, °C	<=26.6
Comfort Heat Index, °F	<=79.9

The difference between the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and the actual Heat Index (HI) is the Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI).

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC),

The publication [4] introduces the “*Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning*” (OCAC), the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

Table 5 - Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), °C

OCAC for Jerusalem, °C	25.4
OCAC for Tel Aviv, °C	25.6

The government of Canada - Natural Resources Canada [3] determines the same parameter with the same value as “*acceptable comfort*”:

- Select the highest thermostat setting that results in acc

The publication “*The comfort and energy impact of overcooled buildings in warm climates*” includes the following observation: “*The average observed temperature recorded through all the selected studies is found to be about 24.0°C. The average comfort temperature calculated for all the selected studies is found to be about 25.5°C*” [9].

Heat Index Control of Air Conditioning

Currently, air conditioning is controlled by the thermostat measuring the temperature of the inlet air, or “I feel” thermostat. Considering only the air temperature and disregarding the air humidity does not guarantee thermal comfort.

To achieve thermal comfort, the thermostat must be set to a lower temperature than needed. Following are examples of energy waste using thermostatic control of air conditioning compared to the Heat Index control, determined with Online Building Energy and Heat Index Simulation and Optimization – BESOO [7].

Table 6 - Energy conservation with Heat Index control

	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Average
Thermostatic Control			
Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), °C	25.40	25.60	
Average Heat Index during cooling, °C	25.02	26.01	
Below the Comfort Heat Index, °C	1.58	0.59	
Minimum Heat Index during cooling, °C	24.26	24.53	
Below the Comfort Heat Index, °C	2.34	2.07	
Cooling hours/y	1,016	2,647	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	824	3,990	
Heat Index Control			
Cooling with Heat Index control, °C	26.98	26.19	
Average Heat Index during cooling, °C	26.60	26.60	
Below the Comfort Heat Index, °C	0.00	0.00	
Minimum Heat Index during cooling, °C	26.60	26.60	
Below the Comfort Heat Index, °C	0.00	0.00	
Cooling hours/y	499	2,383	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	335	3,521	
Energy conservation with Heat Index control			
Decreased cooling hours per year	51%	10%	30%
Energy saving	59%	12%	36%

As demonstrated in the above table, the Heat Index control saves 36% of energy on average between Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, without decreasing the cooling comfort. The saving is a result of increased cooling temperature in hours of lower relative humidity (lower RH), keeping the Heat Index on the comfort level of 26.6°C. 30% of the saving is caused by decreased cooling period, and 6% is related to lower heat transfer through outside walls.

Table 7 - Peak demand mitigation with Heat Index control

	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Average
Thermostatic Control			
Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), °C	25.40	25.60	
Cooling hours/y	1,016	2,647	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	824	3,990	
Max power, kW	1.96	2.98	
PLF	4.8%	15.3%	10.1%
Heat Index Control			
Cooling with Heat Index control, °C	26.98	26.19	
Cooling hours/y	499	2,383	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	335	3,521	
Max power, kW	1.67	2.91	
PLF	2.3%	13.8%	8.1%
Peak demand mitigation with Heat Index control			
	15%	2%	9%

Heat Index control reduces the maximum AC power by 9% on average.

Change of Control Resolution to 0.1 Degree

Currently, the usual control resolution is one degree Celsius or Fahrenheit.

If the user wants to keep the cooling temperature at 25.9°C, and 26.0°C causes thermal discomfort, he must set the cooling temperature to 25.0°C.

The following table demonstrates the energy waste when cooling is operating at 25.0°C instead of 25.5°C.

Table 8 - Energy saving with 0.1 degree remote control resolution

	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Average
Cool on 25.0°C			
Cooling hours/y	1,178	2,927	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	990	4,497	
Cool on 25.5°C			
Cooling hours/y	978	2,695	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	782	4,074	
Energy conservation with 0.1°C resolution			
Decreased cooling hours per year	17%	8%	12%
Energy saving	21%	9%	15%

Change of control resolution to 0.1 degree will bring 15% average energy saving.

12% of the saving is caused by decreased cooling period, and 3% is related to the lower heat transfer through outside walls (related to the reduced temperature difference by 0.5°C).

Table 9 - Peak demand mitigation with 0.1°C resolution

	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Average
Cool on 25.0°C			
Max power	1,178	2,927	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	990	4,497	
Max power, kW	2.11	3.04	
PLF	5.4%	16.9%	11.1%
Cool on 25.5°C			
Cooling hours/y	978	2,695	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	782	4,074	
Max power, kW	1.83	2.99	
PLF	4.9%	15.6%	10.2%
Peak demand mitigation with 0.1°C resolution			
	13%	2%	7%

Change of the control resolution to 0.1 degree reduces the maximum AC power by 7% on average (related to the reduced temperature difference by 0.5°C).

Temperature and Heat Index limits

As mentioned above, the optimum setting of air conditioning to ensure comfort and to minimize overcooling is 25.5°C.

Actually, people all over the world use air conditioning at much lower temperature. According to the energy conservation surveys in Israel, the most popular air conditioning temperature in offices and public buildings is 23.5°C. According to the publication [9], "the average observed temperature recorded through all the selected studies is found to be about 24.0°C".

The issue of increased cooling energy with each Centigrade is described in detail in the publication "Increase in Air Conditioning Energy Consumption with Each Centigrade" [6].

Table 10 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange, %/°C – Jerusalem [6]

Cool On °C	E kWh/y	$\Delta E\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	hrC hr/y	$\Delta \text{hr}\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$\Delta \text{HX}\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$
16	8,004	10.1%	5,473	7.7%	2.2%
17	7,270	11.9%	5,081	8.4%	3.3%
18	6,495	14.0%	4,689	10.2%	3.5%
19	5,697	18.1%	4,256	12.0%	5.5%
20	4,823	26.3%	3,800	16.0%	8.9%
21	3,818	32.4%	3,276	21.2%	9.2%
22	2,884	36.8%	2,702	27.2%	7.5%
23	2,108	42.2%	2,124	30.1%	9.3%
24	1,482	49.7%	1,632	38.5%	8.1%
25	990	66.4%	1,178	48.0%	12.4%
26	595	82.5%	796	63.4%	11.7%
27	326		487		
Ave		35.5%		25.7%	7.4%

E	energy for cooling including condense [kWh/y]
$\Delta E\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	increase of air conditioning energy consumption with 1°C change of setpoint
hrC	cooling hours [hr/y]
$\Delta \text{hr}\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	increase of cooling hours with 1°C change of setpoint
$\Delta \text{HX}\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	increase of heat exchange energy with 1°C change of setpoint

Table 11 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange, %/°C - Tel Aviv [6]

Cool On °C	E kWh/y	$\Delta E\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	hrC hr/y	$\Delta \text{hr}\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$\Delta \text{HX}\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$
16	12,200	7.6%	6,703	6.3%	1.3%
17	11,337	8.4%	6,307	7.0%	1.3%
18	10,461	9.3%	5,895	8.3%	0.9%
19	9,574	9.9%	5,444	8.5%	1.3%
20	8,713	10.8%	5,017	9.1%	1.6%
21	7,865	12.2%	4,599	10.1%	1.9%
22	7,007	14.1%	4,177	11.4%	2.4%
23	6,139	15.6%	3,749	12.2%	3.0%
24	5,309	18.1%	3,340	14.1%	3.5%
25	4,497	22.8%	2,927	19.1%	3.1%
26	3,663	27.1%	2,457	23.7%	2.8%
27	2,882		1,987		
Ave		14.2%		11.8%	2.1%

Table 12 - Average change per 1°C [6]

Cool On, °C	HX	hr	E
16	1.75%	7.00%	8.85%
17	2.30%	7.70%	10.15%
18	2.20%	9.25%	11.65%
19	3.40%	10.25%	14.00%
20	5.25%	12.55%	18.55%
21	5.55%	15.65%	22.30%
22	4.95%	19.30%	25.45%
23	6.15%	21.15%	28.90%
24	5.80%	26.30%	33.90%
25	7.75%	33.55%	44.60%
26	7.25%	43.55%	54.80%
27			
Ave	4.76%	18.75%	24.83%

HX increase of heat exchange energy with 1°C
hr increase of cooling hours per year with 1°C
E increase of thermal energy per year with 1°C

The average increase of energy consumption per year with 1°C in the cooling range 27°C-16°C is 24.8%, consisting of 18.8% increased cooling hours per year and 4.8% increased heat exchange.

There is no reason for any overcooling below the OCAC (25.5°C) or below the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C), however, the regulations allow 3.5°C overcooling to 22.0°C, which is an important improvement from the current 16°C.

Table 13 - Temperature and Heat Index limits equivalent

	RH = 5%	RH = 40%	RH = 100%
Temperature limit, °C	22.00	22.00	22.00
Heat Index (HI), °C	20.39	21.30	22.87
Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), °C	6.21	5.30	3.73
Equivalent limits			
Heat Index (HI) limit, °C	22.80	22.80	22.80
Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), °C	3.80	3.80	3.80
Air temperature, °C	24.19	23.36	21.94

The Heat Index was calculated with the “*Heat Index and Overcooling Heat Index online calculator °C and °F*” on site: <https://nowagreen.ct.ws/HI/>

For the purpose of the saving potential calculations, it is estimated in this work that the use of AC below 22°C is 15% and the weighted average AC temperature in the range 16°C-22°C is 20.5°C.

In the following table, the cooling hours and the energy consumption were calculated using Online Building Energy and Heat Index Simulation and Optimization – BESOO version 544 [7].

Table 14 - Electricity saving by 22.0°C temperature limit per unit

	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Average
Cool on 20.5°C			
Cooling hours/y	3,559	4,808	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	4,356	8,288	
Cool on 22.0°C			
Cooling hours/y	2,702	4,177	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	2,884	7,007	
Energy conservation			
Decreased cooling hours per year	24%	13%	19%
Energy saving	34%	15%	25%

As demonstrated in the above table, the 22°C cooling temperature limit saves 25% of energy on average between Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, without decreasing the cooling comfort. 19% of the saving is caused by decreased cooling period and 6% is related to lower heat transfer through outside walls.

Table 15 - Total saving by 22°C limit

Energy saving per unit	25%
Number of units operating below 22°C	15%
Total saving by 22°C limit	4%

Table 16 - Peak demand mitigation with 22.0°C temperature limit

	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Average
Cool on 20.5°C			
Cooling hours/y	3,559	4,808	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	4,356	8,288	
Max power, kW	2.94	3.43	
PLF	16.9%	27.6%	22.3%
Cool on 22.0°C			
Cooling hours/y	2,702	4,177	
Thermal energy consumption, kWh/y	2,884	7,007	
Max power, kW	2.78	3.31	
PLF	11.9%	24.1%	18.0%
Peak demand mitigation with 22.0°C temperature limit			
	5.6%	3.4%	4.5%
Number of units operating below 22°C			15.0%
Total saving by 22°C limit			0.8%

Separate AC Control for Each Room

The Trane company brings the US Department of Energy estimation of energy saving potential [10]:

“According to the U.S. Department of Energy, HVAC zoning could lead to a 30% reduction in energy costs.”

This is related to the AC systems serving more than one room. In many homes split units are already installed serving only one room. Also in some central AC systems “zoning” is already applied. The following calculation is based on the assumption that at least half of the global energy for cooling is supplied with no option of temperature control or switching off in each room.

Table 17 - Separate AC control for each room

Energy conservation potential per unit	30%
AC without separate control for each room	50%
Total saving	15%

The peak demand mitigation potential was determined using the peak/saving average ratio of other ECMs.

Table 18 - Peak demand mitigation with separate AC control for each room

	Peak	Saving	Peak/Saving
ECM1 = Heat Index control	9%	36%	24%
ECM2 = 0.1 degree control resolution	7%	15%	49%
ECM3 = 22°C limit	0.8%	4%	23%
Ave			32%
ECM4 = separate control for each room	5%	15%	32%

Energy Conservation Potential

Table 19 - Energy conservation potential

Energy Conservation Measure (ECM)	Saving	Sequential ECM Savings	Consumption after ECM
A	B	C = B*D(-1)	D=D(-1) - C
Initial electricity consumption			100.0%
ECM1 = Heat Index control	35.5%	35.5%	64.5%
ECM2 = 0.1 degree control resolution	15.2%	9.8%	54.6%
ECM3 = 22°C limit	3.7%	2.0%	52.6%
ECM4 = separate control for each room	15.0%	7.9%	44.7%
Σ		55.3%	

Table 20 - Global saving

AC global electricity consumption 2022	2,100	TWh/y
Energy conservation potential	55.3%	
Energy conservation potential	1,161	TWh/y
Electricity average tariff	0.10	USD/kWh
Energy conservation potential	116,055,092,059	USD/y

The proposed regulations will save 55% of the global air conditioning electricity consumption, more than 1,000 TWh per year.

The energy conservation measures according to the proposed regulations are in addition to other measures to reduce air conditioning energy consumption, such as:

- improvement of the air conditioning efficiency (Coefficient of Performance)
- improvement of thermal insulation of buildings
- increase of building thermal mass
- motion detectors in rooms to turn off air conditioners in empty rooms
- switching off the power to the air conditioning once or several times a day, requiring manual restarting of the air conditioning in each room
- closing windows and outside doors during air conditioning operation
- cold storage for load shifting

The cost of the measures under the proposed regulations is much lower (if at all) than other measures. At the same time, the impact on energy conservation and mitigation of global warming is much greater.

Peak Demand Mitigation Potential

Table 21 - Global AC peak demand mitigation potential

Energy Conservation Measure (ECM)	Peak demand mitigation	Sequential ECM	Peak after ECM
A	B	C = B*D(-1)	D=D(-1) - C
Initial electricity peak demand for air conditioning			100.0%
ECM1 = Heat Index control	8.5%	8.5%	91.5%
ECM2 = 0.1 degree control resolution	7.5%	6.8%	84.6%
ECM3 = 22°C limit	0.8%	0.7%	83.9%
ECM4 = separate control for each room	4.8%	4.0%	79.9%
Σ		20.1%	

Summer peak demand in Israel in 2025 was 17.3 GW, half of it caused by air conditioning. Mitigation of the national air conditioning peak demand according to the above regulations in Israel would result in 1,700,000,000 USD avoided cost of new power plants, as follows:

Table 22 - Avoided cost of new power plants in Israel 2025

National peak summer demand in Israel 2025	17,300	MW
AC peak demand to national peak demand	50%	
AC peak demand	8,650	MW
AC peak demand mitigation	20.1%	
AC peak demand mitigation potential in Israel	1,738	MW
Natural gas power plant cost in Israel	1,600,000	USD/MW
Conservative approach	1,000,000	USD/MW
Avoided cost of new power plants	1,737,840,467	USD

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